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Effect of palmitic acid-enriched supplements containing stearic or oleic acid on nutrient digestibility and milk production of low and high producing dairy cows

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INTERPRETATIVE SUMMARY

Effect of palmitic acid-enriched supplements containing stearic or oleic acid on nutrient digestibility and production responses of low and high producing dairy cows. *By Burch et al., page XXX.* The objective of our study was to determine the effects of palmitic (C16:0)-enriched supplements containing stearic (C18:0) or oleic (*cis*-9 C18:1) acid on nutrient digestibility and milk production in low- and high-producing cows. Interactions were observed between production level and fatty acid supplementation. High-producing cows increased yields of 3.5% FCM and preformed milk FA when supplemented with a blend of 60% C16:0 + 30% *cis*-9 C18:1. Low-producing cows increased yields of 3.5% FCM, ECM, milk fat and protein, and mixed milk FA when supplemented with a blend of 60% C16:0 + 30% C18:0. Differences observed between low- and high-producing cows indicate that specific fatty acid ratios should be taken into consideration when supplementing cows at different levels of milk production.

Supplemental Table 1. Nutrient intake and nutrient digestibility for cows at different production levels fed treatment diets.¹

Variable	Production Level	Treatment ²			SEM ³	P-value ⁴			Contrasts	
		CON	PA+SA	PA+OA		Trt	Prod	Trt × Prod	CON vs FA	PA+SA vs PA+OA
Digestibility, %										
DM	Low	66.1	68.4	68.6	0.37	<0.001	0.92	0.13	<0.01	0.79
	High	66.1	69.2	67.9					<0.01	0.01
NDF	Low	41.8	43.9	44.0	0.70	<0.001	0.91	0.10	0.07	0.90
	High	41.5	45.7	42.8					0.01	<0.01

¹ Experimental diets fed to 24 cows (12 low cows; 12 high cows) in replicated 3 × 3 Latin squares with 21-d periods and balanced for carryover effects. Samples and data for production variables collected during the last 5 d of each treatment period (d 17 to 21).

² Treatments were: CON = no fatty acid (FA) supplementation, PA+SA = 1.5% of a FA supplement blend providing ~ 60% C16:0 and 30% C18:0, and PA+OA = 1.5% of a FA supplement blend providing ~ 60% C16:0 and 30% *cis*-9 C18:1.

³ Greatest SEM is related to the interaction of production level and treatment.

⁴ P-values refer to the ANOVA results for the fixed effects of treatment (Trt) and production level (Prod), and the interaction of Trt × Prod.

⁵ CON vs. FAT and PA+SA vs. PA+OA contrasts tested the overall effect of FA supplementation and the difference between C18:0 and *cis*-9 C18:1, respectively.

Supplemental Table 2. Milk yield and milk composition for cows at different production levels fed treatment diets.¹

Variable	Production Level	Treatment ²			SEM ³	P-value ⁴			Contrast ⁵	
		CON	PA+SA	PA+OA		Trt	Prod	Trt × Prod	CON vs FA	PA+SA vs PA+OA
Milk yield, kg/d	Low	37.4	38.5	37.6	1.41	0.06	<0.01	0.12	0.33	0.27
	High	52.0	53.1	54.3					0.02	0.15
3.5% FCM ⁶	Low	41.2	42.6	40.9	1.41	0.02	<0.01	0.01	0.38	0.04
	High	51.6	53.1	54.6					<0.01	0.08
ECM ⁷	Low	41.7	43.0	41.2	1.33	0.09	<0.01	0.02	0.57	0.03
	High	52.1	53.3	54.5					0.02	0.14
Fat, kg/d	Low	1.54	1.60	1.52	0.06	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	0.45	0.02
	High	1.80	1.86	1.92					<0.01	0.11
Protein, kg/d	Low	1.34	1.37	1.29	0.04	0.43	<0.01	0.11	0.60	0.02
	High	1.66	1.66	1.68					0.78	0.59
Lactose, kg/d	Low	1.76	1.79	1.75	0.09	0.15	<0.01	0.11	0.69	0.40
	High	2.56	2.61	2.67					0.02	0.14
ECM/DMI	Low	1.29	1.36	1.32	0.04	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	0.03	0.17
	High	1.49	1.55	1.61					<0.01	0.02

¹Experimental diets fed to 24 cows (12 low cows; 12 high cows) in replicated 3 × 3 Latin squares with 21-d periods and balanced for carryover effects. Samples and data for production variables collected during the last 5 d of each treatment period (d 17 to 21).

²Treatments were: CON = no fatty acid (FA) supplementation, PA+SA = 1.5% of a FA supplement blend providing ~ 60% C16:0 and 30% C18:0, and PA+OA = 1.5% of a FA supplement blend providing ~ 60% C16:0 and 30% *cis*-9 C18:1.

³Greatest SEM is related to the interaction of production level and treatment.

⁴P-values refer to the ANOVA results for the fixed effects of treatment (Trt) and production level (Prod), and the interaction of Trt × Prod.

⁵CON vs. FAT and PA+SA vs. PA+OA contrasts tested the overall effect of FA supplementation and the difference between C18:0 and *cis*-9 C18:1, respectively.

⁶Fat-corrected milk; 3.5 % FCM = [(0.4324 × kg milk) + (16.216 × kg milk fat)].

⁷Energy-corrected milk; ECM = [(0.327 × kg milk) + (12.95 × kg milk fat) + (7.20 × kg milk protein)]. This equation corrects milk to a 0.68 Mcal/kg energy basis

Supplemental Table 3. Individual milk fatty acid yields for cows fed treatment diets.¹

Variable	Treatment ²			SEM ³	P-value ⁴			Contrast ⁵	
	CON	PA+SA	PA+OA		Trt	Prod	Trt × Prod	CON vs FA	PA+SA vs PA+OA
Selected individual fatty acids, g/d									
C4:0	40.5	42.4	42.7	1.51	0.02	0.01	0.02	<0.01	0.63
C6:0	30.3	30.3	29.6	1.14	0.38	0.03	0.06	0.46	0.24
C8:0	19.1	18.3	17.5	0.67	<0.01	0.05	0.07	<0.01	0.06
C10:0	55.5	50.3	46.9	1.79	<0.001	0.05	0.13	<0.01	<0.01
C12:0	68.9	60.9	55.9	2.01	<0.001	0.07	0.16	<0.01	<0.01
C14:0	208	200	191	5.13	<0.001	0.001	0.09	<0.01	<0.01
C16:0	594	650	638	24.8	<0.001	0.003	0.03	<0.01	0.16
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	24.4	26.0	24.1	0.86	<0.001	0.50	0.02	0.06	<0.01
C18:0	120	128	130	4.85	0.002	0.07	0.04	<0.01	0.65
<i>trans</i> -6 to -8 C18:1	2.86	3.09	3.82	0.09	<0.001	0.01	<0.001	<0.01	<0.01
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	2.37	2.71	2.96	0.07	<0.001	0.01	0.003	<0.01	<0.01
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	5.19	5.61	6.41	0.41	<0.001	0.08	0.04	<0.01	<0.01
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	7.59	7.41	8.73	0.35	<0.001	0.004	0.01	0.05	<0.01
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	244	264	280	32.7	<0.001	0.01	0.004	<0.01	<0.01
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	33.4	32.3	34.2	0.94	0.01	0.001	0.04	0.76	<0.01
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15 C18:3	5.78	5.48	5.51	0.15	0.03	<0.001	0.06	<0.01	0.78

¹ Experimental diets fed to 24 cows (12 low cows; 12 high cows) in replicated 3 × 3 Latin squares with 21-d periods and balanced for carryover effects. Samples and data for production variables collected during the last 5 d of each treatment period (d 17 to 21).

² Treatments were: CON = no fatty acid (FA) supplementation, PA+SA = 1.5% of a FA supplement blend providing ~ 60% C16:0 and 30% C18:0, and PA+OA = 1.5% of a FA supplement blend providing ~ 60% C16:0 and 30% *cis*-9 C18:1.

³ Greatest SEM related to main effect of treatment.

⁴ P-values refer to the ANOVA results for the fixed effects of treatment (Trt) and production level (Prod), and the interaction of Trt × Prod.

⁵ CON vs. FAT and PA+SA vs. PA+OA contrasts tested the overall effect of FA supplementation and the difference between C18:0 and *cis*-9 C18:1, respectively.

Supplemental Table 4. Individual milk fatty acid content for cows fed treatment diets.¹

Variable	Treatment ²			SEM ³	P-value ⁴			Contrast ⁵	
	CON	PA+SA	PA+OA		Trt	Prod	Trt × Prod	CON vs FA	PA+SA vs PA+OA
Selected individual fatty acids, g/100 g									
C4:0	2.58	2.59	2.63	0.06	0.21	0.45	0.73	0.25	0.17
C6:0	1.93	1.85	1.82	0.04	<0.001	0.91	0.46	<0.01	0.17
C8:0	1.22	1.12	1.08	0.02	<0.001	0.52	0.32	<0.01	0.01
C10:0	3.56	3.08	2.89	0.06	<0.001	0.28	0.25	<0.01	<0.01
C12:0	4.42	3.75	3.46	0.06	<0.001	0.06	0.23	<0.01	<0.01
C14:0	13.3	12.4	11.8	0.15	<0.001	0.53	0.86	<0.01	<0.01
C16:0	37.7	39.9	39.4	0.47	<0.001	0.15	0.21	<0.01	0.03
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	1.56	1.63	1.51	0.05	0.01	0.03	0.23	0.06	<0.01
C18:0	7.68	7.87	8.04	0.21	0.03	0.40	0.67	0.02	0.19
<i>trans</i> -6 to -8 C18:1	0.18	0.19	0.24	0.01	<0.001	0.95	0.15	<0.01	<0.01
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	0.15	0.17	0.19	0.01	<0.001	0.87	0.74	<0.01	<0.01
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	0.34	0.37	0.41	0.04	0.02	0.97	0.60	0.02	<0.01
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	0.49	0.46	0.55	0.02	<0.001	0.49	0.12	0.94	<0.01
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	15.7	16.4	17.4	0.24	<0.001	0.16	0.70	<0.01	<0.01
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	2.15	2.00	2.13	0.6	<0.001	0.54	0.31	<0.01	<0.01
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15 C18:3	0.37	0.34	0.34	0.01	<0.001	0.41	0.63	<0.01	0.37

¹ Experimental diets fed to 24 cows (12 low cows; 12 high cows) in replicated 3 × 3 Latin squares with 21-d periods and balanced for carryover effects. Samples and data for production variables collected during the last 5 d of each treatment period (d 17 to 21).

² Treatments were: CON = no fatty acid (FA) supplementation, PA+SA = 1.5% of a FA supplement blend providing ~ 60% C16:0 and 30% C18:0, and PA+OA = 1.5% of a FA supplement blend providing ~ 60% C16:0 and 30% *cis*-9 C18:1.

³ Greatest SEM related to main effect of treatment.

⁴ P-values refer to the ANOVA results for the fixed effects of treatment (Trt) and production level (Prod), and the interaction of Trt × Prod.

⁵ CON vs. FAT and PA+SA vs. PA+OA contrasts tested the overall effect of FA supplementation and the difference between C18:0 and *cis*-9 C18:1, respectively.

Supplemental Table 5. Milk fatty acid yields for cows at different production levels fed treatment diets (n = 24).¹

Variable	Production Level	Treatment ²			SEM ³	P-value ⁴			Contrast ⁵	
		CON	PA+SA	PA+OA		Trt	Prod	Trt × Prod	CON vs FA	PA+SA vs PA+OA
Summation by source, g/d										
<16-Carbon	Low	407	387	351	16.6	<0.001	0.001	0.06	<0.01	<0.01
	High	466	446	441						
16-Carbon	Low	559	617	582	29.4	<0.001	0.003	0.03	<0.01	<0.01
	High	678	735	742						
>16-Carbon	Low	478	498	494	16.5	<0.001	0.001	0.001	0.08	0.74
	High	542	565	615						

¹ Experimental diets fed to 24 cows (12 low cows; 12 high cows) in replicated 3 × 3 Latin squares with 21-d periods and balanced for carryover effects. Samples and data for production variables collected during the last 5 d of each treatment period (d 17 to 21).

² Treatments were: CON = no fatty acid (FA) supplementation, PA+SA = 1.5% of a FA supplement blend providing ~ 60% C16:0 and 30% C18:0, and PA+OA = 1.5% of a FA supplement blend providing ~ 60% C16:0 and 30% *cis*-9 C18:1.

³ Greatest SEM is related to the interaction of production level and treatment.

⁴ P-values refer to the ANOVA results for the fixed effects of treatment (Trt; denominator df= 42) and production level (Prod), and the interaction of Trt × Prod.

⁵ CON vs. FAT and PA+SA vs. PA+OA contrasts tested the overall effect of FA supplementation and the difference between C18:0 and *cis*-9 C18:1, respectively.

Supplemental Table 6. Insulin concentration for cows fed treatment diets.¹

Variable	Treatment ²			SEM ³	P-value ⁴			Contrasts ⁵	
	CON	PA+SA	PA+OA		Trt	Prod	Trt × Prod	CON vs FA	PA+SA vs PA+OA
Insulin, µg/L	0.57	0.52	0.54	0.03	0.22	0.02	0.44	0.14	0.44

¹ Experimental diets fed to 24 cows (12 low cows; 12 high cows) in replicated 3 × 3 Latin squares with 21-d periods and balanced for carryover effects. Samples and data for production variables collected during the last 5 d of each treatment period (d 17 to 21).

² Treatments were: CON = no fatty acid (FA) supplementation, PA+SA = 1.5% of a FA supplement blend providing ~ 60% C16:0 and 30% C18:0, and PA+OA = 1.5% of a FA supplement blend providing ~ 60% C16:0 and 30% *cis*-9 C18:1.

³ Greatest SEM related to main effect of treatment.

⁴ P-values refer to the ANOVA results for the fixed effects of treatment (Trt) and production level (Prod), and the interaction of Trt × Prod.

⁵ CON vs. FAT and PA+SA vs. PA+OA contrasts tested the overall effect of FA supplementation and the difference between C18:0 and *cis*-9 C18:1, respectively.